

GREEN HRM - A PATHWAY LEADING TO THE GROWTH OF ORGANISATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Environmental, Ecological and conservative supportability are the two significant contemplations for a business to effectively work. Green HRM rehearses join both the elements of business supportability. It makes mindfulness among representatives to execute the Go Green drive at the workplace. The current exploration accentuates Green HR practices and Green Building. They drive development with invigorating and planet-accommodating arrangements and spotlight on Green Buildings, Living Green, Smart Building, and Green HRM rehearses like power saving, having paperless workplaces by utilizing applications, software& e-hr, squander reusing, and so forth. It underlines harmless to the ecosystem practices and decreasing carbon impression. The primary critical objective of the paper is to inspect the level of green exercises carried out by associations and determine the viability of green HR systems. This subjective review depends on a multi-method approach where writing survey and Interview plan technique were utilized with HR directors of the organization as members. The review features the need to take on the execution of ecological manageability and green structure ideas on a higher scale, top up with the rising demo natural resources.

Keywords: Green HRM, Green Buildings, Carbon footprint, Planet-friendly solutions, sustainability.

Introduction

Environmental resources have consistently ended up being a help for humankind as are their purposes. In any case, as the world pushed forward through current developments and cutting edge advancements, the unwavering quality on these regular assets has arrived at its pinnacle. Also, presently the greatest test for humanity is to support these assets. As individuals go through these assets, they are likewise answerable for safeguarding there the people in the future. Many exploration discoveries show that where organizations take on mediations that lead to climate the board, which helps in superior business marking, cost decrease, and in this way expanded deals and benefits (Srivastava, 1995; Christmann, 2000; Khanna and Anton, 2002)

As per (Hussain et al,2018), for association particle to perform effectively, there is a positive need to think about manageability s one of the centre standards. The possibility of ecological maintainability for the most part manages the drawn out soundness of our fair biological system, asset protection for the ages to come, contributing more motel sustainable power, and turning around the overabundance carbon delivered in the climate because of man-made exercises and the relating results, for example, an unnatural weather change a greenhouse use impacts. Supporting the climate would likewise help utilizelizing the regular assets admirably, subsequently safeguarding different assorted species and keeping up with natural equilibrium.

As the populace the of human race expands, the per capita utilization increments proportionately, and the method for addressing these necessities, more urbanization and industrialization are advanced. Prompting which individuals have wound up decaying and dirtying the regular method for water and air. Besides, the high level strategies for portfolio need of grains, beats, vegetables, and so on, individuals have caused a lot of soil contamination all over the planet. These assets are likewise being defiled with poisonous synthetics and contaminations, in this way making endurance a trouble for the people in the future. The hurtful poisons and synthetic compounds delivered in them, has driven all the intensity to get caught near the outer layer of the planet, lea ding to extreme expansion in the temperature. The intensity that is getting from the Sun is assumed test back subsequent to giving the necessary warmth. Yet, because of the abundance carbon in the climate, this intensity gets caught in the environment driving the two nursery impact. As per an exploration puncture prescription by United States Development Authority (USDA) and Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), this impact will bring about a temperature increment of over 2°C continuously 2050. With the assistance of the most recent innovations and gadgets, it is effectively ready to evaluate the effect and the results, yet what everybody Nexfor ds to look is, to track down a green answer for this multitude of issues. A biotechnological and green methodology reed for the tracking down the answers for these biological issues.

Environment, Social being the three mainstays of the multi-faceted idea the Sustainability, as characterized by United Nations, many organizations have been attempting to produce benefit by offering more towards their obligations or society and the climate. In other worth ecological manageability associates mindfulness for long haul affordable and social turn of events, accordingly idiot proofing the groundwork of efficient advancement by firmly associating individuals and ether environment.

Organizations in ongoing past are thinking of procedures for offering more transcended ecological supportability by creating administrative trends to remember the manageability for decision making to meet the arising needs to keep up with associations with partners. Consequently, adding Environmental Sustainability as another bearing of technique. A rising

pattern of associations is being made liable for climate the executives, because of the expanded event of normal disasters (Rondinelli and Berry, 2000). Aside from keeping away from legitimate consequence by following the green methodology, green HRM rehearses helps in building all-encompassing maintainability in associations (Pavitra, 2017)

The concept of Green HRM

Green HRM alludes to utilization of Human Resource Management approaches for advancing ecological supportability inside the associations. Implanting the ecological perspectives in HR sub capabilities from enlistment to exit is perceived as Green HRM (Jabbour et al ,2010) to rehearsing the reasonable usage of assets inside business associations. Organizations have been advancing the execution of Green HRM in their HRM strategies. Furthermore, these strategies essentially spin around the development, application and proceeding with conservation of a framework, with a way to deal with make workers of the association, Green. The commitments made by green representatives towards ecological supportability, can help the individual, the general public, the climate and the business as entirety. The green HRM essentially manages the approaches and practices to assist the typical representatives with changing green. These representatives can contribute towards the climate by playing both of the jobs - preservationist, progressive, non-polluter, or producer. Furthermore, the green HRM will effectively create, improving and holding this green idea inside the workers of the association.

The green HRM can assume immediate and vital part in producing green workforce that essentially have mindfulness about green exercises, rehearses and values the green creativities and subsequently, jam its green objectives generally through the Human Resource Management cycle of recruiting, utilizing, learning and improvement and worker remunerations, and accordingly in a roundabout way propelling the association's human resources. The green HRM arrangements advocate the reasonable use of normal assets inside associations and thusly advances the benefits of climate manageability. These arrangements advance the accepted procedures and ideal frameworks that assist the representatives with practicing environmental safety and contribute towards the climate in this way helping the individual, society and the association. The Green HRM on a very basic level means a green methodology towards to the everyday and normal work we follow. The more we practice environmental awareness, the better we do the climate. The green HRM can likewise be considered as a statement which makes progress toward the advancement of green labor force that can comprehend and value green culture in an association. The HR division has been assuming a critical part in presenting the green culture in the associations, without anyone else making an interpretation of the Green strategies into training, and in this way setting a model.

Green Building:

The buildings that are built keeping environment in mind are considered as green buildings. Green buildings are constructed with high quality materials and have a low environmental impact. These buildings are basically designed, built, and operated in such a way that they eliminate negative environmental impacts and create a positive effect on our climate. The green building also fulfils the criterion of being built with least exploitation of the natural resources and creating an eco-friendly impact on the environment. Moreover, green Constructions that are constructed remembering climate are considered as green structures. The green structures are worked with top notch developments and lower natural effect. These structures are fundamentally planned, developed and worked in such a way that it kills the adverse consequences on the climate and establishes a constructive outcome of our environment. The green structure additionally satisfies the measure of being worked with least abuse of the regular assets and making an eco-accommodating effect on the climate. Besides, green structures contain a few better highlights associated with green practices, for example, proficiency of energy, environmentally friendly power and the board of tempest water. As of late, a few businesses have embraced the Green structure for their associations at a flawless speed. Also, as the Green structure costs excessively less, when contrasted with the ones constructed the customary way, this would add monetary advantages to the organization.

The green structures are assembled utilizing the reasonable engineering strategy that fundamentally focuses on the hurtful effect of the structure on the climate. Likewise, this engineering strategy lessens the effect of the structures on the climate, right from the start of the area determination to the life-cycle end destruction of the structure. Indian Green Building Council (IGBC) was arrangement in 2001 as a piece of Confederation of Indian Industry (CII).

There are still several organisations that certify that organisation and assist building developers in implementing green principles and obtaining green certification. LEED-India, IGBC Ratings, BEE-ECBC, and TERI GRIHA are a few examples.

The review is done in view of a product improvement specialist organization in Coimbatore, Tamilnadu. The organization's product is globally prestigious CAFM/EAM/CMMS programming that is rivalled world conspicuous items in the Facility Management space. The organization is working with brilliant structures for decreasing the energy wastage, space, and expands the resource life to help for lessening the office's functional expenses considerably. The organization is world's second biggest greenest structure. In this organization normal assets utilized in an ideal way and immaterial carbon impressions. The organization has acknowledged green way of thinking solidly; it is areas of strength for joined and front line. Green structures assist its tenants with becoming independent and work on the capacity to

make due in non-ideal circumstances. The organization comprehends that there are a ton of basic perspectives that can undoubtedly carry out to practice environmental safety and the organization chose to share all learning through numerous stages and set up an extremely durable green learning community at the grounds for individuals to adjust, duplicate and make do.

Source ; Conceptual model of S-HRM (adapted from Macke and Genari [6]).

Literature review

Green HRM

G Mandip (2012) notices the climate and level of Green HR creativities complete by ITC Limited as a contextual investigation. The discoveries uncovered that the emphasis on further developing the functional efficiencies joined with up - degree of innovation have driven ITC to accomplish the achievements of being carbon positive, water positive and accomplishing practically 100 percent strong waste reusing.

The paper completed by D Renwick, T Redman and S Maguire (2013) goes through the compositions on Environmental Management and Human Resource Management, and introduced a cycle model and examination plan progressing in Green Human Resource Management. The outcomes uncovered that future exploration in to Green HRM might offer energizing results focused on all investors in Human Resource Management. For bosses and experts these might be to make the utility of including laborers support and contribution in natural administration exercises to better-quality hierarchical environmental execution, conceivably through a definite consideration on squander the executives and reutilizing for associations and laborers, they may perhaps help entryway businesses to acknowledge Green

HRM systems and exercises that advantage to keep up with and further develop worker well-being and wellbeing for teachers, they might reveal additional realities to expand a Human Resource Management part to the data base on Green Management overall.

The research by S Sudin (2011) recommends an expansion of a new model of strategic green HRM by studying of works on Human Resource characteristics of ecological management, combining the thinking rising from the analysis of these works and recommend research model. From the viewpoints of strategic Human Resource Management and green management, the study claims that the new model must consist among others the relationship of assessment – based Human Resource interventions, Environmental Management System, Green Intellectual Capital and Corporate Environmental Citizenship.

A Arulrajah, H Opatha & N Nawaratne (2014) reviewed green HRM practices and revealed that Human Resource Management has more possibility and opportunity in enhancing organization's eco-friendly performance and this analysis unites varied purposes of HRM to discover relevant green HRM practices in the twelve roles of Human Resource Management such as job plan, job examination, workforce planning, staffing, selection, orientation, performance assessment, learning and development, compensation management, discipline management, wellbeing and safety management and workers relations.

S Rani & K Mishra (2014) made an attempt to encourage the significance Green HR contains, that is, two important components eco-friendly Human Resource practices and protection of information resources. The outcomes comprised of: electronic filling, virtual conferences and teleconferencing, drive sharing, work sharing, reutilizing, teleworking, virtual training, and improving additional energy effective workplaces. Scholar has tried to emphasis on the implementation of green HR practices in organizations. This research has also assisted the scholar to recognize the areas like learning and development, performance assessment system and some fixed actions where on application of this idea of Green HRM takes place.

W Donohue and N Torugsa (2016) used data from 158 minor companies in the Australian equipment manufacturing sector and machinery to investigate the moderating effect of Green HRM on the relationship between proactive ecological management and monetary performance in minor companies. When compared to low levels of Green HRM, higher levels of Green HRM increase the monetary benefits of proactive ecological management. The research also demonstrates the added value that Green HRM provides when used as an enabler of proactive ecological management.

K Mehta and P K Chugan (2015) talks about the current improvements of Green HRM exercises in firms in light of results from some explores, overview data and optional data from firms web sources and they also brings the accessible job of HRM capabilities for framing green standards in the organizations. Discoveries uncovered that tolerant conservational

rehearses help the organizations to set aside cash and find imaginative wellsprings of exchange and stay safe. Green firms believe that it is more savvy to practice environmental awareness than it is to remain imperiling the climate and it likewise assisted the organizations with working on their public connections and appearance which additionally impacts incomes

D Bangwal & P Tiwari (2015) aimed to offer awareness on how Green HRM can benefit or influence the workers and their business activities and behaviour in contradiction of atmosphere and they also suggest certain societal implications of Green HR practices for green organisations. The findings were Green HRM can improve readiness, motivation and obligation to workers to contribute their hard work and thoughts to the greening of their organisations. The efforts for Green Human Resource Management resulted in improved effectiveness, ecological usage of properties, fewer consumption, work connected approach, better work / private life, lesser expenses, better workers performance and retention which benefit organisation to lessen workers carbon footprints by the mean of Green HRM.

P Kapil (2015) made an effort to learn the ecological sustainability activities implemented by three top car manufacturers of India and its effect in constructing an all-inclusive mind set for producing a culture of sustainability. Findings revealed that TATA motors has attempted to decrease its waste, indulge a lot in to reusing stuffs and reduced intake of non- renewable bases of energy and they involves their workforces in greener practices and were stern in its effort to be eco - friendly. Maruti Suzuki has arisen with petroleum efficient means of transportation and they were able to reduce the CO2 emissions over the years because of the emergence of alternate fuel technologies. Mahindra began producing electric cars with excellent mileage in order to reduce the carbon footprint, and they emphasised the concept of the green value chain, thus adding green value at every stage of the model. They also promote the use of renewable energy and efficient water management.

Green Building sustainable practices

The book by J Yudelson named 'The Green Building Revolution' (2010) presents about green structure and the turns of events and people that are advancing to this endeavor. It shows why and how it begins to be smart about arranging, building and working incredible execution, environmentally responsive LEED - affirmed developments on regular funds. Green structure shows the better entryway conditions that utilization definitely less energy and water than regular structures do.

CJ Kibert (2016) passes on inside and out data on all attributes of the green structure strategy structure assets assortment to developing frameworks and that's just the beginning. Green structures capability at an exceptionally extraordinary degree of productivity which is arranged promising simply by mindful consideration in each phase of the strategy. Feasible structure offers unadulterated course for all pieces of green structure, along with the best

most recent turns of events and the freshest innovation and reasonable land utilization, finishing, building fixings, situating, water use assumes a principal part in the structures last carbon impression.

A J Hoffman and R Henn (2008) claims that harmless to the ecosystem development in the structure plan and development industry will keep on slowing down in the event that the significant cultural and mental obstacles that proceed are not tended to. They review in the administrative, individual and hierarchical level and settled with approaches for conquering them. Issue cultivating, holding back nothing, preparing, functional and impetus variety, safeguarding risk, green development standard turns of events and duty change are the techniques proposed by the creators.

M Samari, N Godrati, R Esmailifar, P Olfat and M Shafiei (2013) expect to investigate the degree of developing green structure in the current condition , to find huge vital participants and to perceive and eliminate the fundamental confusions to the development of green structure . Principal boundaries found were nonappearance of credit assets to safeguard front and center expense, risk of resource, nonattendance of interest as well as more noteworthy completing worth. Organization jobs particularly impetus instruments, for example, underlying motivations, refund program, appropriation, charge motivator plot, low revenue contract advance, deliberate rating framework and commercial center and innovation are the significant drives for eliminating hindrances to green structure development, creators recommended.

Q Ma, RZ Wang, YJ Dai, and XQ Zai (2006) investigated the performance of a hybrid air conditioning system. It was according to the green building demonstration project's hybrid building energy system. It was the Shanghai project. The results show that at a latent load of 30%, this system outperforms a conventional vapour compression system by 44.5%. And with a latent load of 42%, this improvement can be achieved by 73.8%.

R J Yang, P Zou & J Wang (2016) aimed to plan the collaborating networks of the threats related with diverse shareholders in green building developments and to achieve an understanding of the main danger networks and the study was conducted in china and Australia. Findings revealed that while risk of reputation is significant in both nations, the moral threat of valuation understanding and justice has been emphasized as crucial in the Chinese environment and the management shows an important part in developing the culture's understanding and consciousness on green knowledge interest in China. The value and truthfulness of shareholder and threat investigation by demystifying the societal complication which is generally overlooked in old-fashioned linear risk influence examination is improved by the societal network examination technique in this study.

Some contradictory studies were also reviewed:

W.L. Paul & P.A. Taylor (2008) conducted a study comparing the comfort and satisfaction of occupants in environmentally friendly and conventional buildings. To test this, they measured occupant comfort and satisfaction. They took samples from a leafy university building and his two conventional buildings. They used questionnaires for their research. Residents were asked to rate the working environment. There was no evidence that green buildings were more convenient. The only difference between buildings was that residents of green buildings were more likely to describe the workplace atmosphere as warm and bad. However, the building's hot water cooling system failed during the study period, so this result cannot be generalized as a change between environmentally friendly and conventional buildings. All other comfort features such as sex and humidity were not perceived differently by occupants of the two building types

C K Chau, M S Tse, and K Y Chung (2010) found that environmentally savvy residents have varying preferences and levels of willingness to pay to improve several attributes of green building performance. We effectively conducted a multiple-choice experiment to show whether Results showed that there was no significant change in preferences between green and conventional residents for energy savings, improved indoor air quality, noise reduction, landscape enhancement or water conservation. They also found that green residents were willing to pay significantly less than conventional residents for the expansion of the landscape portion of residential developments, although this was more It was seen as one of the key factors that distinguishes development from conventional development.

Empowering the employees with going Green was found to have a positive impact on Green HR practices in organizations (Yusliza *et al* 2017). However, Greener HR is found to be challenging due to the presence of multiple policies and practices (Jackson et al, 2014)

The above literature review indicates that there is more scope for researches in the green concepts of organizations. Green HRM and Green building as an organizational sustainability measure is under researched (Daily and Huang, 2001; Renwick et al., 2013), it becomes paramount to consider the topic as the research interest . Besides, research studies on Green HR is predominantly western and less Asian, leaving room for research in developing nations. (Renwick et al, 2013).

The study discusses on respondents showed a positive attitude towards green building. It is more employee friendly and organisation friendly. As green HRM and green buildings are more environment friendly and people are more dependent on environment more detailed studies can be conducted to know the advantages of green concepts, employee satisfaction, employee preferences, barriers for implementation etc.

Source: <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7099/9/2/75/htm>

Research methodology

The research is on the basis of primary data and also secondary data which are collected through different sources. primary data is collected from the Director and five HR managers of software development service provider companies using structured interview schedule. Duration of the interview with each participant was 45 minutes on an average .Interviews were recorded with prior consent of the participants. Field notes were also taken whenever necessary. Interviews questions were structured and open ended, with an aim to capture the current HRM practices in their organisations. Some of the questions asked using structured interview were,

- 1) What are the green practices followed by the company?
- 2) How this entire idea of green building makes an impact on the workforce and company?
- 3) What is your opinion about green buildings and what you recommend for the people?

After the participants' response, the researcher paraphrased the points to ensure correctness in noting down the points. The responses are discussed in the findings and discussions part.

Apart from this the secondary data is collected from various publishes research papers, journals, books and print media. Research literatures available from last two decades were considered for review, with an accent on reviews of last five years.

Green Building is a part of Green HRM practices. This research paper mainly focused on green building as the researchers were provided with primary data through interview.

A COVID-19 Exposer

The study reveals, that COVID-19 was discovered to play the role of an exposer, showing significant disparities in the treatment of employees depending on their gender, color, aptitude, and social class. For instance, women and people of color, who make up a disproportionately large share of the care workforce, are more likely to be exposed to the hazards of catching the coronavirus. Additionally, gig workers], blue-collar workers, those employed in the hotel, tourism, and production industries, as well as those who lost their jobs, had more job instability, had lower incomes, and experienced career shocks were the most negatively impacted. Additionally, there is more chance for employee group divisions. Two conceptual articles revealed incense with particular groups. COVID-19 has confronted workers with previously unheard-of difficulties. Performance by De Cieri and Lazarova

A Disruptor: COVID-19

A study investigating the relationship between COVID-19 and sustainable HRM focused on HRM systems, with 22 articles focusing on this trend. Vacation practices, employee turnover and retention, training and development during COVID-19, and compensation and benefits were some of the HRM practices covered. Further studies used HRM as a system to examine how pandemics interacted with his HRM. they. Examining the impact of his socially responsible HRM on pandemic-induced employee anxiety, Manuti et al. Examine the impact of HRM on constructive behavior in an organization. in the field of HRM practices and systems

Findings and discussion

The employee's prioritization is more on decreasing the dependency on fossil fuels. Electronic automobiles, two wheelers and car - sharing is encouraged. The company provides only 7% parking space for cars. 20% employees are staying at a walk able distance. This reduces the travel cost.

Free shuttles and subsidised workers housing in the vicinity benefited to decrease the carbon footprint. The fully automated visitor management system in the company requires just a few formalities. A mobile number, an instant OTP and selfie and generate access cards for pre visitors and for repeat visitors. Visitors can also use NFC (Near Field Communication) enabled phones to gain faster access. Others can flash their vising cards at the camera to register. Natural lighting leads to better health and better efficiency. Smart use of natural light brings down the need for artificial lighting. In the company day light in 86% of regularly occupied space is used during normal work hours. 97% occupants have a natural view.

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The company also give preference for intelligent window shades. Most of the workplace shades are regulated by hand and somewhat inefficiently. Workers either have them shut at all times thus not having natural sunlight. They also tend to leave them open making more heat flow during the day and light pollution at night. In this company advanced somfy suntracking or shadow controlling system tracks the sun and outside sunlight conditions to raise and lower the shades. It also regulates the angles of the blind to maximise daylight entry while regulating glare and heat gain. . The app give workers the ability to physically regulate the shades too when required.

Healthier natural sunlight and excellent sights result in improved workers' productivity. Other highlight of the company is efficient air conditioning and superior indoor quality. Well-organized administration of heat load brings down the problem on air conditioning and save electricity. A clean and fresh workspace makes better health and productivity. But air conditioning is one of the biggest power takers in an office. It invariably fills enclosed spaces with stale micro bleeding air and forces the system to constantly pump in fresh air leading to energy loss. The facility uses a variable refrigerant flow system which with its precise temperature control makes for 55% more energy efficiency than other systems. It offers an energy efficiency ratio of 13.85%. Sensors fixed across the building continuously monitor temperature levels. Heat recovery ventilation systems helps to make the musty air out and gets refreshed air in. Heat transfer between hot fresh air and cold exhaust air reduces air conditioning load and electricity consumption. Foobot, a real-time Internet of Things sensor, monitors the levels of volatile organic compounds, humidity, and particulate matter 2.5 throughout the building. This data is used by the company software, which controls the HRV to adjust the supply of fresh air.

More indoor plants are kept as they make the air fresh. They save water by the zerodor waterless urinals. The brainy system allows only one way flow liquids and vapours; this eliminates the need to flush and saves water in the process. Aerators and sensor fitted taps is used for reduced water flow.

Wastage of paper is found to be one of the major concerns for organisations (Pavitra ,2017). The company follows a zero paper towel policy to save trees and also reduce methane gas production from decomposing paper towels.

In the company the food is cooked with mostly organic produced that is sourced fresh. The kitchen uses 100% electric equipment eliminating fossil fuel usage. This includes an energy efficient refrigerator, dishwasher that uses the lower quantity of the water, automated water

saving taps and locally builds highly energy efficient fans aptly called superfan. All the cleaning products are chemical free too. The kitchen and dining area also gets day light. The canteen management system makes a smart kitchen. The kitchen order tracking, live consumption, kitchen inventory, procurement and kitchen waste monitoring functions are managed by the system.

Raw water and rain water filtration systems are fully automated. Water is used in the gardens and restrooms. The organization focuses on paperless office and follows it. 100% waste segregation happens at each stage and recycling automatically follows. Organic waste from kitchen is converted in to highly nutrient manual and takes care of the entire requirement of the garden. 25% of the site area is covered by vegetation. Roof top garden produces organic vegetables for kitchen. Meeting room reservation, registration of external attendees, parking lot allotment and event timely catering is managed seamlessly by the Facility booking system.

Recommendations

These are the first hand information from the Director and HR manager of the company considered for the study.

They responded that the green building impacts the employees as the company gives more importance to occupant wellness thus by improving occupant health and reducing mental fatigue. 86% day light and 97% natural view ensures that. They encourage physical activity by promoting staircase use with signage prompting to walk. Thicker walls / glass panels ensure better acoustic comfort. In house cafeteria which provides nutritious, hygienic, freshly made, home style subsidised food ensures the better health of the employee which results in healthier people and healthier organization. It also reduces attrition levels and unplanned sick leaves. Employees are motivated to work in a place like this. It increases the productivity of occupants.

They also recommend that actually green buildings are not expensive to build even it is understood like that. They saved a lot on the capital cost. Design optimization of day lighting, natural views, automation, all these resulted in reduction in air conditioning capacity and lighting, 50% in their case. And also there is huge reduction in the energy demand as well. With a good budget they achieve all this and they spend extra only on automation part and some technology demonstrators. They strongly feel just by applying the right strategies and enough awareness without spending more any building can achieve the gold rating level. This means every single corporate building in India can Go Green.

The organizations should adopt the implementation of environmental sustainability and green building concepts on higher scale, to cope up with the increasing demand of the natural resources. In the India, technologically advanced cities like Bangalore, Chennai, New Delhi, etc. incorporating the Green HRM and Green Building policies, can make huge difference, as

these cities are, considered to be, the major IT hubs in the country. Due to lack of awareness and knowledge about Green principles, still there are majority of companies, who haven't yet adopted these policies. Thus, an initiative must be taken to increase such awareness and educate the organizations with perks of going green.

A clean and fresh workplace is always considered as an ideal work area for blooming ideas and better work-life balance. The employees working in green environment can in-turn increase the productivity for the organization, and this being the reason why the organization should invest on green initiatives. These initiatives can create tremendous impact towards the benefit of the environmental resources and help preserve them. In Bangalore as there are lot of companies, employees are also lot more. As a part of green, the employees of the organization can be encouraged to use car-pooling, public transport, electric scooters and bicycles.

Organisations should start implementing the green concept to help build a healthier, prosperous and sustainable future; by understanding the importance of green movement. Likewise hospitality property can be greener, as green initiatives are not so expensive through implementing green buildings we can reduce energy, water and waste. In addition with the cost benefits there are also other benefits in choosing the environmental sustainable strategy, these can include gaining a competitive advantage in the industry being a leader, Customer loyalty, Employee retention and Awards & Recognition.

Organizations can get recognized at global level for adopting the green policies and implementing them, setting an example for other organizations to participate in the initiative. This way the sustainability of the natural resources will be increased substantially, and the exploitation of the natural resources will be reduced, to great extent. Adopting green policies will help the companies to save a large amount of their financial funds, and reduce the waste generation too.

As mentioned in the recommendations, if the organizations are implementing and following green practices it will create a better environment that leads to sustainability and better living. Global warming is the earth's biggest challenge. People, vehicles and buildings are becoming the cause for it. Green growth is even better for the planet and for the people. The findings of the study underline the importance of Green HRM practices and Green Building. It helps to improve the employee morale, employee faithfulness, and recognition of a brand, also increases employee productivity, efficiency, and motivation and retention of workers. The research highlights the positive impact of green HR on organizational climate. The study findings of positive contribution of Green HR practices for organizational sustainability is corroborated by the study on 121 firms of manufacturing sector, which found a similar outcome (*Zaid et al 2018*)

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is definite need for organisations to go green for greater sustainability. Environmental training as well as enforcing green practices in the HR sub-functions will go a long way in building a greater employer brand and goodwill, which are the bedrock of Organizational sustainability.

References

1. Bangwal, D., & Tiwari, P. (2015). *Green HRM—A way to green the environment*. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 17(12), 45-53.
2. Bryman, A. (2004), *Social Research Methods*, 2nd Ed., Oxford University Press, Oxford.
3. Chau, C. K., Tse, M. S., & Chung, K. Y. (2010). *A choice experiment to estimate the effect of green experience on preferences and willingness to pay for green building attributes*. *Building and Environment*, 45(11), 2553-2561.
4. Christmann, P. (2000), "Effects of "best practices" of environmental management on cost advantage: the role of complementary assets", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 43 No. 4, pp. 663-680
5. Daily, B.F. and Huang, S.C. (2001), "Achieving sustainability through attention to human resource factors in environmental management", *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 21 No. 12, pp. 1539-1552.
6. Gowri, K. (2004). *Green building rating systems: An overview*. *ASHRAE Journal*, 46(11), 56.
7. Guerci, M., Longoni, A., & Luzzini, D. (2016). *Translating stakeholder pressures into environmental performance—the mediating role of green HRM practices*. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(2), 262-289.
8. Hoffman, A. J., & Henn, R. (2008). *Overcoming the social and psychological barriers to green building*. *Organization & Environment*, 21(4), 390-419
9. Kapil, P. (2015). *Green HRM-Engaging Human Resource in reducing carbon footprint and enhancing environment sustainability: A case study based approach*. *International Journal of Engineering Technology Science and Research*, 2(5), 14.
10. Kats, G. (2003). *Green building costs and financial benefits (p. 1)*. Boston, MA: Massachusetts Technology Collaborative.
11. Khanna, M. and Anton, W.R.Q. (2002), "Corporate environmental management: regulatory and marketbased incentives", *Land Economics*, Vol. 78 No. 4, pp. 539-558.
12. Kibert, C. J. (2016). *Sustainable construction: green building design and delivery*. John Wiley & Sons.
13. Ma, Q., Wang, R. Z., Dai, Y. J., & Zhai, X. Q. (2006). *Performance analysis on a hybrid air-conditioning system of a green building*. *Energy and Buildings*, 38(5), 447-453.
14. Mandip, G. (2012). *Green HRM: People management commitment to environmental sustainability*. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, ISSN, 2277, 2502.

15. Mehta, K., & Chugan, P. K. (2015). *Green HRM in pursuit of environmentally sustainable business. Pursuit of Environmentally Sustainable Business* (June 1, 2015). *Universal Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 3(3), 74-81.
16. Mishra, R. K., Sarkar, S., & Kiranmai, J. (2014). *Green HRM: innovative approach in Indian public enterprises. World Review of Science, Technology and Sustainable Development*, 11(1), 26-42.
17. O'Donohue, W., & Torugsa, N. (2016). *The moderating effect of 'Green'HRM on the association between proactive environmental management and financial performance in small firms. The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(2), 239-261.
18. Opatha, H. H. P., & Arulrajah, A. A. (2014). *Green human resource management: Simplified general reflections. International Business Research*, 7(8), 101.
19. Paul, W. L., & Taylor, P. A. (2008). *A comparison of occupant comfort and satisfaction between a green building and a conventional building. Building and environment*, 43(11), 1858-1870.
20. Pavitra Mishra, (2017) "Green human resource management: A framework for sustainable organizational development in an emerging economy", *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, Vol. 25 Issue: 5, pp.762-788, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-11-2016-1079>
21. Pillai, R., & Sivathanu, B. (2014). *Green human resource management. Zenith International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(1), 72-82.
22. Rani, S., & Mishra, K. (2014). *Green HRM: Practices and strategic implementation in the organizations. International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 2(11), 3633-3639.
23. Renwick, D. W., Redman, T., & Maguire, S. (2013). *Green human resource management: A review and research agenda. International Journal of Management Reviews*, 15(1), 1-14.
24. Rondinelli, D.A. and Berry, M.A. (2000), "Environmental citizenship in multinational corporations: social responsibility and sustainable development", *European Management Journal*, Vol. 18 No. 1, pp. 70-84
25. Samari, M., Godrati, N., Esmailifar, R., Olfat, P., & Shafiei, M. W. M. (2013). *The investigation of the barriers in developing green building in Malaysia. Modern Applied Science*, 7(2), 1
26. Sharma, K. (2016). *Conceptualization of green HRM and green HRM practices: Commitment to environment sustainability. International Journal of Advanced Scientific Research and Management*, 1(8), 74-81.
27. Sharma, R., & Gupta, N. (2015, January). *Green HRM: an innovative approach to environmental sustainability. In Proceeding of the Twelfth AIMS International Conference on Management* (pp. 2-5).
28. Shrivastava, P. (1995), "The role of corporations in achieving ecological sustainability", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 20 No. 4, pp. 936-960

29. Sudin, S. (2011, June). *Strategic green HRM: A proposed model that supports corporate environmental citizenship*. In *International Conference on Sociality and Economics Development, IPEDR (Vol. 10, pp. 79-83)*.
30. Yang, R. J., Zou, P. X., & Wang, J. (2016). *Modelling stakeholder-associated risk networks in green building projects*. *International journal of project management*, 34(1), 66-81.
31. Yudelson, J. (2010). *The green building revolution*. Island Press.
32. Zuo, J., & Zhao, Z. Y. (2014). *Green building research—current status and future agenda: A review*. *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 30, 271-281.
33. Yusliza, M.-Y., Othman, N.Z. and Jabbour, C.J.C. (2017), "Deciphering the implementation of green human resource management in an emerging economy", *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 36 No. 10, pp. 1230-1246. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMD-01-2017-0027>
34. Jabbour, C. J. C., Santos, F. C. A. & Nagano, M. S. (2010). *Contributions of HRM throughout the stages of environmental management: Methodological triangulation applied to companies in Brazil*. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 21(7), 1049–1089. doi:10.1080/09585191003783512
35. Jackson, S. E., Schuler, R. S. & Jiang, K. (2014). *An aspirational framework for strategic human resource management*. *The Academy of Management Annals*, 8(1), 1-56.
36. Zaid, A. A., Jaaron, A. A. M., & Talib Bon, A. (2018). *The impact of green human resource management and green supply chain management practices on sustainable performance: An empirical study*. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.09.062
37. Hussain, N., Rigoni, U., Orij, R. P., 2018. *Corporate governance and sustainability performance: Analysis of triple bottom line performance*. *J. Bus. Ethic.* 149 (2),411-432